

Abstract

How much GDP does a company like Costco Wholesale generate on a global basis? This article presents a simple methodology for calculating indirect GDP without double-counting economic activity, and example calculations.

Keywords: GDP, Methodology, Statistics, Costco Wholesale

JEL Codes:

A1 - General Economics

B4 - Economic Methodology

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D2 - Production and Organizations

D4 - Market Structure, Pricing, and Design

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L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy

N3 - Labor and Consumers, Demography, Education, Health, Welfare, Income, Wealth, Religion, and Philanthropy

P11 - Planning, Coordination, and Reform

P16 - Political Economy

Methods to Estimate Global GDP Impact from Costco Wholesale

How much GDP does a company like Costco Wholesale generate on a global basis? This article presents a simple methodology for calculating direct and indirect GDP without double-counting economic activity. It also provides example calculations from Costco's financial statements.

Costco Wholesale Corporation (2025) presents high-level economic statistics in its financial statements. Costco reports total global revenue of \$254 billion for the fiscal year 2024. If we estimate GDP impact as equal to total revenue, then we will double-count the amounts Costco paid for cost of goods sold when aggregating across companies. Instead, we calculate the value-added portion of Costco's operation to estimate the direct GDP as follows.

I describe three channels through which Costco Wholesale contributes to GDP, with one example of direct GDP and two examples of indirect GDP.

The direct GDP impact is measured as value-added activity, the difference between revenues and cost of goods sold. The 2024 revenues were \$254 billion versus merchandise costs of \$222 billion. Costco's value-added activity totalled \$32 billion, and this is an estimate of Costco's direct GDP contribution. These are broad categories that don't capture indirect GDP contributions or capital costs. Combines a variety of factors for production, like consumables, capital repairs, and labour. It would help to have a detailed breakdown of where this \$32 billion goes, so we can follow the money and track how its velocity changes as it moves. People with lower income generally have a higher velocity of money. Greater elasticity for consumption at lower income, but higher incomes have elasticity in savings. Money with slow velocity can have a positive economic impact if spent on long-term investment, but the effect on GDP will be in the distant future.

One type of indirect GDP is a sequence in which the same dollar is spent several times within the same year. A series of calculations of the value-added amount for transactions that pay the same dollar as the original direct GDP impact. This channel can be small if the velocity of money is low, or can be larger than 1x if the velocity of money is sufficiently high. Unclear what

multiplier values are for Costco Wholesale. I'd guess a 0.5x multiplier to start, which would increase indirect GDP by approximately \$16 billion.

The second type of indirect GDP is a channel through financial markets. Costco Wholesale's membership program is like a shareholder relationship, where customers have an interest in the store's success. Customers need to buy a membership; imagine if they also had to buy stock? There is potential for a significant wealth effect among Costco Wholesale's long-term shareholders.

Costco Wholesale shareholders are approximately 52% retail individual investors. How many of those investors are also members of Costco? I assume that 60% of the retail shareholders are also members, and then estimate that 30% of Costco Wholesale's shareholders are also members. This is a rare and essential feature in capital markets, where a special company has a firm conviction in its customers. For example, Warren Buffett put this idea into action by investing in companies he understood and patronized.

Costco's total market cap is around \$400 billion. I assume 30% of shareholders are also members, and they own \$120 billion worth of Costco shares together. They experience a positive wealth effect from owning Costco shares. Although these gains are generally unrealized, I assume these shareholders sell some of their stock each year to fund increased shopping at Costco, based on the wealth effect of rising values of their Costco shares over time.

I assume member-shareholders will spend 5% of the gross value of their Costco shares each year, or \$6 billion in consumer spending from the member-shareholders who own 30% of Costco shares. Count this entire amount as indirect GDP contribution, or assume only part of this spending counts towards GDP based on the value-added economics of the place where the money is spent. Assume all \$6 billion gets spent at Costco again and compare with prior results. Recall that Costco had \$32 billion in value-added GDP from \$254 billion in total revenue, yielding a 12.5% value-added-to-revenue ratio. In this scenario, with \$6 billion in new revenue, the incremental value-added GDP is \$750 million.

I estimate \$49 billion equals the total GDP impact of Costco worldwide. This is \$32 billion in direct GDP plus \$16 billion in indirect GDP from labour and \$0.75 billion in indirect GDP from the wealth effect.

Figure 1: Long-term Stock Chart of Costco Wholesale

I am not satisfied that this is an accurate assessment for several reasons. For one, the financial data from Costco is highly aggregated and does not allow a detailed breakdown of cost types. There are investment analysts with accurate models of all aspects of Costco's operations, and I would like to see more detailed models that follow the money more closely to see how much is spent on what, and how much of that spending contributes to GDP. Consider that direct GDP includes operating income and retained earnings, which are not part of GDP. Economic accounting is complicated, and I challenge other economists to improve methods to estimate the GDP impact of companies like Costco based on their financial reporting, in line with GAAP standards.

References

Costco Wholesale Corporation (2025), "Costco Wholesale 2024 Annual Report,"

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